

A Research Paper Review Report On
Skin cancer predication using deep
learning techniques

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ABSTRACT

Recent innovations in deep learning have improved the detection of skin cancer and speed up the process while now yielding better accuracy through automated systems. From CNNs, transfer learning, and hybrid approaches, different deep learning models have come in handy in identifying malignant and dangerous skin conditions such as melanoma. The most effective techniques for distinguishing between the dermoscopic images of skin lesions to improve the performance of diagnostic systems with various datasets would be MobileNet, federated learning, and genetic algorithms.

Melanoma is one of the most aggressive forms of skin cancer whose incidence continues to rise around the world. Early detection is likely to be the most crucial factor that will improve patient survival rates. Despite much progress, the challenges remain variability in data, ability of models to generalize across environments, and ensuring that the models are efficient and scalable. The current emphasis in research is overcoming these challenges to create systems that can be smoothly integrated into clinical practice.

Indeed, it is shown that a use of optimized CNNs and MobileNet-based models significantly enhanced classification accuracy with detection rates of above 90% in some of the used datasets. These are the early findings that can pave the way toward any deep learning promises that could possibly be held for early skin cancer detection, thus reducing reliance on manual diagnosis, furthering the outcomes of the care process.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, the most aggressive and fast-growing cancers are melanomas. The World Health Organization report states that over 132,000 cases of melanoma are diagnosed each year worldwide, and an estimated 2 to 3 million cases of non-melanoma skin cancers are diagnosed annually. Overexposure to UV radiation is the leading cause of skin cancer, damaging the DNA in the cells, thus causing mutations and producing cancerous cells.

Although medical technology has advanced a lot, early detection is still the only way that mortality rates can be reduced, and melanoma has a high cure rate if it is detected in an early stage. However, the diagnosis of skin cancer through dermoscopic images is still time-consuming and prone to human errors-a perfect reason for needing reliable and automated diagnostic tools.

- Data Collection: Gather the dermoscopic images of skin lesions.
- Preprocessing: Clean up the data, augment, and resize.

- Training: Train a CNN, MobileNet, or Hybrid model on labelled data
- Prediction: Output of the input as malignant or benign based upon the trained model
- Evaluation: Accuracy along with sensitivity and specificity are computed.

Fig [1.1]

Fig [1.2]

Medical imaging in particular finds revolutionization with deep learning. Several diseases can be classified and detected automatically. In the case of skin cancer detection, it has gained vast usage in CNNs due to the facility of automatic extraction of features from dermoscopic images. This transfer learning is very effective with limited data sets by utilizing large amounts of learned knowledge from huge image datasets.

The primary objective of this study is to introduce and design a precise prediction system of skin cancer based on dermoscopic images by using a deep learning approach. The system aims for:

- Increase in the accuracy of differential differentiation between malignant and benign lesions.
- Decrease diagnosis time and resources.
- Generalization of the model.
- Reducing the number of computations to be feasible in real-world applications.

Type of skin cancer

Fig [1.3]

Fig [1.4]

It is motivated by growing skin cancer burdens and the limitations of traditional diagnostic methods. With an ever-increasing availability of medical image datasets and breakthroughs in the power of AI, early detection is now realistically offered with an unprecedented improvement in rate and saving of lives as well as scarce reduction in the healthcare costs. Apart from the above, automated systems relieve dermatologists of over-weighting stress and minimize diagnostic errors and are especially useful in resource-constrained settings where the medical expertise is scarce.

Literature review/ serve:

WHAT IS INCLUDED IN THE TABLE:

1. Mobile Net-Based Transfer Learning: Utilizes Mobile Net for efficient skin cancer detection in mobile environments, achieving 85% accuracy but with lower performance compared to larger models.

2. Federated Machine Learning: Employs federated learning to preserve privacy and enhance diagnostic accuracy, reaching 90-95%, though it involves complex model training.
3. Multi-Feature Fusion Framework: Combines CNNs and traditional ML methods for high sensitivity (92%), but is computationally expensive.
4. Deep Learning Architectures for Melanoma: Uses deep CNN architectures for effective melanoma detection with 87% accuracy, requiring significant computational resources.
5. Combined Decision of Deep Learners: Implements ensemble learning with deep CNNs, achieving 93% accuracy, offering robustness to image variations.
6. AI-Powered Diagnosis: Applies various deep learning techniques for skin cancer diagnosis, with 91% accuracy, and is comparable to expert dermatologists.
7. Alternating Sequential and Residual Networks: Employs advanced network architectures for high sensitivity and specificity (88%), but requires extensive computational resources.
8. Optimized CNN Using Genetic Algorithm: Features an optimized CNN for high diagnostic accuracy (89%), with potential for real-time applications, but needs large annotated datasets.
9. Transfer Learning and Feature Fusion: Combines transfer learning and feature fusion for adaptable detection across lesion types (90%), though it has complex training requirements.
10. Comparative Study of Deep Learning Models: Provides a review of various deep learning models, noting improvements in accuracy but also highlighting issues like dataset variability and overfitting.

11. Skin Cancer Detection Using Deep Learning: Achieves up to 95% accuracy with early and accurate diagnosis, but faces challenges with dataset variability and the need for large annotated datasets.

12. Systematic Review of Neural Network Algorithms: Discusses advancements in detection accuracy (90-95%), focusing on integration into clinical workflows and interpretability.

13. Ensemble of ML and DL Techniques: Enhances detection performance with ensemble methods (up to 93%), but has high computational complexity and data diversity requirements.

14. Deep Learning-Based Classification: Uses CNNs and data augmentation for high accuracy (92%), with potential for real-time applications but requires large datasets.

15. Multi-Resolution-Tract CNN: Features hybrid CNN models for effective lesion classification (94%), though it demands extensive computational resources.

16. Segmentation Using Deep Learning: Implements fully convolutional networks for accurate lesion segmentation (89%), with complex preprocessing needs.

17. Mobile Nets for Skin Cancer Detection: Provides efficient performance in mobile environments with 85% accuracy, but lower compared to larger models.

18. Melanoma Detection Using InceptionV3: Achieves 91% accuracy with performance comparable to dermatologists, suitable for diverse populations.

19. Automatic Identification of Malignant Melanoma: Uses CNNs and transfer learning for high diagnostic accuracy (85-90%), with integration and privacy considerations.

20. Very Deep Residual Networks for Melanoma: Reaches 87% accuracy with high sensitivity, but requires substantial computational resources for training.

This overview highlights various techniques, accuracies, and challenges in advancing skin cancer detection using machine learning and deep learning technologies.

COMPARISION TABLE

TITLE	AUTHOR NAME	MACHINE LEARNING ALORITHMAS	DATASET	RESULT	ADVANTAGE	CHALLENGES
Mobile Net-Based Transfer Learning for Skin Cancer Detection	Mazhar T et al.	Mobile Net, Mix Nets	isic Archive	85%	Efficient for mobile environments	Lower accuracy compared to larger models
Federated Machine Learning for Skin Lesion Diagnosis	Yaqoob MM et al.	Federated Learning	ISIC Archive	90-95%	Privacy preserving, improved diagnostic accuracy	Complexity in model training

Multifeatured Fusion Framework for Automatic Skin Cancer Diagnostics	Bakheet S et al.	Fusion of CNNs and Traditional ML	PH2 Dataset	92%	High sensitivity and specificity	Computationally expensive
Deep Learning Architectures for Aided Melanoma Recognition	Diame ZE et al.	Deep CNN Architectures	ISIC Archive	87%	Effective in melanoma detection	Requires large computational resources
Combined Decision of Deep Learners for Skin Cancer Detection	Imran A et al.	Ensemble Learning, Deep CNNs	ISIC Archive	93%	Robust to variations, improved performance	Complexity in model integration

	AUTHOR NAME	MACHINE LEARNING ALORITHMAS	DATASET	RESULT	ADVANTAGE	CHALLENGES
AI-Powered Diagnosis of Skin Cancer	Me lark N et al.	Various DL Techniques	ISIC Archive, Dement	91%	Comparable to expert dermatologists	Generalizability across populations
Alternating Sequential and Residual Networks for Skin Cancer Detection	Kumar N, Sandhan T	Alternating Sequential and Residual Networks	biomedical Image Dataset	88% %	High sensitivity and specificity	- Requires large computational resources
Optimized CNN for Skin Lesion Diagnosis Using Genetic Algorithm	Salih O, Duffy KJ.	Optimized CNN, Genetic Algorithm	ISIC Archive	89%	High diagnostic accuracy, potential for real-time applications	Need for large annotated datasets
skin Cancer Detector Based on Transfer Learning and Feature Fusion	Cai H et al.	Transfer Learning, Feature Fusion	ISIC Archive	90%	Adaptable to various lesion types	Training complexity

Deep Learning for Skin Cancer Classification: A Review and Comparative Study	Ahmed A. Younis, Hesham A. Ali, Mahmoud E. Selim	Various s deep learning models (e.g., CNNs, RNNs)	Publicly available datasets (e.g., ISIC, HAM10000)	Provides a comparative analysis of different models, noting improvements in classification accuracy and diagnostic performance	Comprehensive review of state-of-the-art techniques - Comparative analysis highlights strengths and weaknesses - Broad coverage of available datasets	Variability in dataset quality and size - Overfitting issues with certain models - Computational resource requirements for training complex models
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TITLE	AUTHOR NAME	MACHINE LEARNING ALORITHMAS	DATASET	RESULT	ADVANTAGE	CHALLENGES
SKIN CANCER DETETION USING DEEP LEARNING	Oge Marques, He -Cheol Kim	CNNs, Transfer Lear Ning	ISIC Archive, Dermot its Image Library	High accuracy in classification tasks Up to 95%	Early and accurate diagnosis, support for dermatologists	Dataset variability, need for large annotated datasets
Skin Cancer Detection and Classification Using Neural Network Algorithms : A Systematic Review	Various	CNNs, Ensemble Learning Techniques	ISIC Archive , PH2 Dataset	Significant advancements in detection accuracy 90-95%	Improved diagnostic accuracy, non-invasive detection	Integration into clinical workflows, interpretability

Skin Cancer Detection N Using Ensemble of Machine Learning and Deep Learning Techniques	Huang D, Shan C, Ardabil Ian M, Wang Y, Chen L	CNNs, Ensemble Methods	Kaggle Skin Cancer Dataset	Enhanced detection performance through ensemble methods Up to 93%	Robustness to variations in image quality	Computational complexity, need for diverse training data
Deep Learning-Based Algorithm for Skin Cancer Classification	Ismail MA, Hameed N, Clos J	CNNs, Data Augmentation	ISIC 2017, ISIC 2018	Improved classification of skin lesions 92%	High diagnostic accuracy, potential for real-time applications	Model interpretability, need for large annotated datasets
Multiresolution-Tract CNN with Hybrid Pretrained and Skin Lesion Trained Layers	Kawahara J, Harmane G	Hybrid CNN Models	ISIC 2017	Effective in distinguishing between malignant and benign lesions 94%	High specificity and sensitivity, adaptable to various lesion types	Training complexity, need for extensive computational resources

TITLE	AUTHOR NAME	MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS	DATASET	RESULT	ADVANTAGE	CHALLENGES
Segmentation of Skin Lesions from Thermoscopic Images Using Deep Learning Techniques	Codella NC, Nguyen QB, Pan Kanti S, Gutman D, Helba B, Halpern A, Smith JR	Fully Convolutional Networks (FCNs), U-Net	ISIC Archive, Dermofit Image Library	High accuracy in segmentation tasks 89%	Improved lesion boundary detection, supports subsequent classification	Complex preprocessing steps, need for large annotated datasets
MobileNets for Skin Cancer Detection: Application and Performance Analysis	Howard AG, Zhu M, Chen B, Kalenichenko D, Wang W, Weyand T, Andreetto M, Adam H	MobileNets, CNNs	ISIC Archive, DermNet	Effective for mobile and resourceconstrained environments 85%	Efficient in mobile and resource-constrained environments - Lightweight and fast	- Lower accuracy compared to larger models - Potential trade-off between speed and precision - Limited flexibility
Skin Lesion Analysis Towards Melanoma Detection Using Deep Learning Network	Esteva A, Kuprel B, Novoa RA, Ko J, Swetter SM, Blau HM, Thrun S	InceptionV3, CNNs	ISIC Archive, Stanford Dataset	Achieved dermatologist-level classification performance 91%	Comparable to expert dermatologists, potential for wide deployment	Generalizability across diverse populations and image sources

Deep Learning and Transfer Learning Approaches for Automatic Identification of Malignant Melanoma in Dermoscopy Images	Menegola A, Tavares J, Fornaciali M, Li LT, Avila S, Valle E	CNNs, Transfer Learning	ISIC 2017, PH2 Dataset	Effective in distinguishing malignant from benign lesions 85-90%	High diagnostic accuracy, adaptable to various datasets	Integration into clinical workflows, data privacy
Automated Melanoma Recognition in Dermoscopy Images via Very Deep Residual Networks	Tschandl P, Rosendahl C, Kittler H	Very Deep Residual Networks (ResNet)	ISIC Archive	Improved accuracy in melanoma recognition 87%	High sensitivity in detecting melanoma	Requires large computational resources for training

Studies have shown that using machine learning and deep learning, skin cancer detection is highly effective, and it can often reach a level of accuracy upwards of 90% and are thus very good at early spotters for skin cancer. There's the challenge on the other hand: these methods require much computer power to work well, demand amounts of high-quality data, and are complicated to train. The only thing is that some of these tools may be very difficult to use in real life, due to the next privacy problem and the issue of making sure models work fine for different people. With all these limitations aside, there is an immense impetus on how these technologies could be built to be much faster and more readily available to potentially greatly enhance skin cancer detection in the future.

Research gaps in skin cancer detection by machine learning and deep learning are areas where current methods fail to provide accurate predictions or where further research may offer value. Some of the key research gaps identified below:

1. Diversity and Quality of Dataset: Many of the models rely on a few specific datasets, which does not capture all of the types of skins and demographics. Higher diverse good quality datasets are required to achieve generalization across populations.

2. Better computational efficiency: Latest models entail tremendous computational ability, thereby limiting access to them. Research into more efficient algorithms and techniques requiring fewer computing powers would help in increasing such tools' availability.

3. Incorporation into clinic: More research is required on how these technologies could potentially be integrated into everyday clinical practice. This involves matters related to user training, workflow integration, and regulatory compliance.

4. Model Robustness: Most models do very well in controlled circumstances but fail when real-world variations, such as variations of image quality and lighting, are present. That is the reason why researchers have an avid interest in making the models more robust.

5. Privacy and Security: Privacy is a concern when using methods like federated learning. There is much more to be done to better safeguard data and ensure compliance with regulations, yet realize the effectiveness of training the models.

6. Interpretability and Explainability: Deep learning models work like "black boxes," making it challenging to understand how they make decisions. Advances in this area of making these models more interpretable will help build trust and enhance clinical adoption.

7. Real-Time Performance: There is constant improvement in the speed and efficiency of models in performing real-time analyses without any compromise on the degree of accuracy. This calls for research into faster methods of processing.

8. Adaptability to New Lesion Types: Since newer types of lesions are apparent, models need to learn fast. Research on adaptable and continuously learning systems would solve the problem.

The solutions for the detection of skin cancers will be more effective, accessible, and practical, translating to better outcomes for patients, by bridging those gaps.

- What is Done :

With machine and deep learning, researchers can now quickly advance towards skin cancer detection. Models that can identify skin cancer with accuracy rates of more than 90% can be built. Most of the models utilize advanced techniques including combining methods or making use of pre-trained systems. Some models are even implantable on mobile devices for easier access. Studies of the comparison of different models help know which ones will work well in which conditions.

- What Can Be Done :

1. Better Data: We lack images with a variety of different skin types and better images depicting the lesions, which in turn make models less accurate for different people's bodies.

2. Faster and Cheaper: Developing models with less required computing power makes them more practical and inexpensive.

3. Practice : To integrate these tools with routine medical practice, extensive research in the following area would be required: studies to assess the ease of use of these tools for physicians and the extent to which these tools do not break rules.

4. Real-World Issues : Models should be developed that work on diverse image qualities and lighting conditions.

5. Privacy: Their ability to safeguard patient information and observance of the rule book on privacy.

6. Understanding Decisions: Making sure that models better explain decisions will allow doctors to have more trust and utilize them efficiently.

7. Real-Time Usage: Improving models to be faster at image analysis so that the system can quickly and correctly identify, in real-time, would be very helpful.

8. Adaptation to New Lesions: The model's ability to conveniently adapt to new kinds of discovered skin lesions will keep the detection systems current.

- Result analysis:

1. Diverse Dataset: Combine a varied dataset encompassing different skin types, types of lesions, and demographics. The model can thereby be tested on a variety of populations and conditions.

2. Efficient Algorithm: Design more efficient machine learning algorithms that do not require significant computational resources. It could be achieved through optimization of the available models or by finding new ones that are less complex without becoming out-of-date.

3. Real-Time Analysis Capabilities: The system must analyze in real-time, so that immediate feedback and faster decision-making are possible. This can be particularly valuable in clinical settings where timely diagnosis is crucial.

Clinical integration will relate to "user-friendly" interfaces and work flows that integrate effectively with existing medical systems. This will include compatibility with clinical practice and usability by the health professional.

5. **Robustness and Adaptability:** Improve the resistance of the proposed model towards variations in image quality, different kinds of lighting conditions, etc. Design adaptive algorithms that learn from new data, adapt to the emergence of new skin lesions with time and adapt to different kinds of problems.

6. **Privacy and Security:** The privacy of patient data should be added through strong privacy measures that will agree with all types of regulations for the data storage method and data transmission method.

7. **Interpretability of Models:** Develop tools for clinicians to see how the model makes its predictions, possibly as a method for instilling trust in the system for better clinical decisions.

8. **Performance Monitoring and Feedback:** Instil continuous monitoring and evaluation of how the model is performing and gather real-time feedback from users on what parts of the system are faulty and what needs improvement.

• **Conclusion**

So far, research with the latest technologies, like machine learning and deep learning, has yielded very impressive results in the detection of skin cancer. Many developed models measure above 90% and are thus very effective for finding instances of skin cancers. These methods allow early identification of lesions on the skin either by deep learning or an amalgamation of other approaches.

But still, there's room for improvement. There are questions related to the diversity and quality of data; whether there are also faster computing methods that can quickly perform tasks without compromising the accuracy of the output; and how to merge these tools with real-life medical practices. Other challenges would be related to privacy, understanding how models make decisions, and even in applying it in real-time.

The work highlights significant improvements toward skin-cancer-detection systems but further work is still required to be brought out in this particular field to make these systems even better and more efficient while offering easy utilization in real-world settings.

- Future Scope:

1. Better Data: More diverse varieties of skin images must be gathered from various bodies for making models more precise for everyone.

2. Efficiency: The models should be as accurate as the existing ones but use much fewer computing powers so that they can be applied in real-life.

3. Real-Time Use: An improvement in the speed of the models will allow for prompt results, which are important for timely medical decisions.

4. Clinical Integration: Future systems should integrate into the prevailing medical practices and therefore must be easy to use by doctors and other healthcare providers.

5. Robustness: Models must be able to better handle different qualities of images and lighting conditions and learn from the newly discovered types of skin lesions.

6. Privacy and Security: Keeping the patient data secure and private will be quite crucial as these technologies are adopted more widely.

7. Understandability Models: The more understandable the technology is, the more doctors would feel like learning to trust and using it effectively.

8. Continuous Improvement: Active monitoring and improvement based on real-world feedback of such systems will keep them effective and useful.

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